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Diet Composition and Condition Factor of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* in the Cross River Estuary

By

**George U. U.
Idung J. U.
Andem A. B.
Okorafor K. A.
Mowang D.**

Research Article

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*George U. U., Idung J. U., Andem A. B., Okorafor K. A.,
Mowang D.

Department of Zoology & Environmental Biology, University of Calabar, Calabar.

*Correspondence Author's Email: gboy4Jesus@yahoo.com, Phone: 08032625310

ABSTRACT

The food and feeding habits of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* in the Cross River Estuary was studied between November and January, 2011. Result revealed that the species feed mostly on food from plant origin, although food from animal materials was also identified. A total of 120 plant materials (31.49%) were consumed by the species, algae 58 (15.22%), diatoms 44 (11.54%), Food from animal origin encounter in the gut of the species as incidental diets components included fish eggs 22 (5.71%), fish scales 14 (3.67%), fish bones 17 (4.95%), and Aquatic insects part 40 (10.49%). Unidentified food items encountered in the gut of the species during the study were 16 (3.67%), mud/sand particles 50 (13.12%) and detritus which could not be enumerated. The condition factor calculated for the species varied during the studies period with a mean value of 2.0 in November, 3.10 in December and 1.98 in January. Based on the food items isolated in the gut, the species could be considered as a voracious herbivore in the Cross River Estuary. While the variation in the condition factor of the species in the Estuary may indicate a period of high yield or otherwise of the species in the system.

Keywords: *Ethmalosa fimbriata*, Diet composition, Condition factor, Cross River Estuary, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the food and feeding habits of fresh water fish species is a subject of continuous research because it constitutes the basis for the development of a successful fisheries management programmed on fish capture and culture (Oransaye and Nakpodia, 2005). Nature offer a great diversity of organisms that are used as food by fish, and these differ in size and taxonomy group (Olojo *et al.*, 2003). The dietary analysis of organism in their natural habitat enhances the understanding of the growth, abundance, productivity and distribution of organisms (Fagade and Olaniyan 1972).

The diet of cultured species does not provide precise and reliable information on the food, feeding habits and condition factor of such species. Hence, most studies which are aimed at obtaining such information on food, feeding ecology and condition index of organisms are based on the analysis of gut content of organism caught from their natural habitats (Longhurst, 1957, Job and Udo, 2002, odum, 1971).

Ethmalosa fimbriata belongs to the phylum chordata, subphylum: vertebrata, class: Actinoptergii and it is a pelagic clupeiformes belonging to the family clupeidae. It occurs in fresh water and brackish water environment. Clupeids are among the commercially exploited fishes for human consumption especially in Africa due to their cheap rate.

Condition factor has been used as an index of growth and feeding intensity (Fagade, 1979). Condition factor decrease with increase in length (Fagade, 1979) and also influence the reproduction cycle in fish (Welcome, 1979). Condition factor of fish is an important fishery management tool. Its importance is pronounced in estimating the relative well-being of a fish population in a particular river system.

A study of the diet composition and condition factor of *E. fimbriata* from the Cross River estuary adds more information on the family, clupeidae to complement the existing data in the management and culture of the species in Cross River State.

MATERIALS AND METHOD**Study Area**

The fish specimens were collected from the Cross River Estuary (Fig 1). The Cross River estuary is formed from numerous tributaries arising from the western slope of the Cameroon Mountain which have two spurs in

Nigeria as Oban hills in the South and Obudu hills in the North (Moses, 1988). It is observed that the main river enters Nigeria from the Cameroon and flows first in a west-ward direction then turns south-wards and enters the Atlantic Ocean with limited Delta formation (Moses, 1988). The whole Cross River estuary lies approximately between longitudes $7^{\circ}30'E$ and $10^{\circ}00'E$ and latitude 4° and $8^{\circ}N$. The river basin cover an area of $54,008\text{km}^2$ of which $14,000\text{km}^2$ lies in the Cameroon and $39,500\text{km}^2$ in Nigeria. The cross river basin is located within the high forest belt of southern Nigeria. Rainfall is almost all year round but is heaviest from April to October. Dry season occur from November to March. Annual rainfall is in the region of 3000mm around the Estuary. The River is subjected to seasonal flooding and about $8,000\text{km}^2$ of the basin within Nigeria comes under flood. The fish of Cross River estuary is rich and varied.

Figure 1: Map of the Cross River Estuary

Sample Collection

Samples of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* were collected on a monthly basis for three months (November–January, 2011) at Nsidung beach (along Calabar river) and Abitu beach (along Great Kwa river), from the landing of basket trap fisheries of the artisanal fisherman. A total of seventy five (75) freshly caught fish belonging to different size classes were collected. The samples were stored in an ice chest on each day of sampling and taken to the institute of oceanography laboratory for analysis.

Analysis

The standard lengths (beginning from snout to end of caudal peduncle) (Schneider, 1990) were taken to the nearest 0.1cm using a standard measuring board. The wet weight was taken with an electronic weighing balance (Mettler P-1210N) to the nearest 0.1g. The weight of each fish was matched against the corresponding length (cm). The individual fish gut was carefully extracted by cutting open the abdominal portion of the fish with the aid of a pointed nose pair of scissors. The gut (tip of Oesophagus to the end of the rectum; Lagler *et. al.*, 1977) was carefully removed by use of forceps.

Determination of Food Volume

The food volume of each gut was determined by displacement method (Hyslop, 1980). This was done by placing 10ml of distilled water in a 50ml capacity glass cylinder. Each gut was individually dropped in the water

contained in a glass cylinder. The quantity of water displaced by the gut represented the food volume in the gut. This was matched with the individual fish length and weight which were previously taken.

Determination of Diet Components

Each gut was preserved in glass bottle containing 10% formaldehyde prior to the determination of diet components. The preservation of the gut in 10% formaldehyde enhanced the coagulation of the diet components for ease of identification (Longhurst, 1957, Haroon, 1998, Job, 2006). The content of each gut was scrapped with a spatula into a glass Petri-dish and examined with a stereo microscope. The diet components from each gut were enumerated and the total number noted for each diet group.

Determination of relative percentage occurrence of diet components

$$\% RA = \frac{n}{N} \times 100 \text{ (Marioghae, 1982)}$$

Where;

%RA = Relative percentage occurrence
n = number of individuals diet component
N = total number of all diet component identified from the gut

Determination of condition factor (k)

Condition factor (k) (the degree of fatness or corpulence or well – being of a specimen).

$$K = \frac{W}{L^3} \times 100 \text{ (Ricker, 1971)}$$

Where;

K = condition factor
W = wet weight (g) of each specimen
L = length (cm) of each specimen.

RESULTS

Condition factor index (K)

The length, weight, food volume and condition indices of the species for the study period are shown in table 1a to 1c. The total condition factor of the species in November was 50.0 with mean of 2.0. In December total condition factor was 77.6 with mean of 3.10 while in January total condition factor was 49.41 with mean of 1.98.

Table 1a: **Length (cm) Weight (g) Food Volume (ml) Condition Factors (k) and Diet Composition of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the Cross River Estuary, Nigeria. (November, 2010)**

S/n	Total length(m)	Wet weight(g)	Food volume(mc)	Condition factor(k)
1	18.5	100	5.0	1.58
2	17.5	100	5.0	1.86
3	18.0	120	6.0	2.05
4	17.0	100	4.0	2.04
5	17.0	80	4.0	1.63
6	18.0	100	5.0	1.71
7	17.0	80	4.0	1.63
8	17.0	100	6.0	2.04
9	17.0	120	6.0	2.44
10	16.0	80	4.0	1.95
11	18.0	140	8.0	2.40
12	18.0	120	6.0	2.05
13	17.0	140	8.0	2.85
14	20.0	160	6.0	2.0
15	17.0	60	3.0	1.22
16	20.0	140	5.0	1.75
17	15.0	120	5.0	3.56
18	20.0	160	6.0	2.0
19	19.0	120	6.0	1.75
20	19.0	140	8.0	2.04
21	18.0	120	6.0	2.05
22	17.0	100	5.0	2.04
23	17.0	80	4.0	1.63
24	16.0	80	4.0	1.95
25	15.0	60	3.0	1.78
Total				50.0
Mean				2.0

Table 1b: **Length (cm) Weight (g) Food Volume (ml) Condition Factors (k) and Diet Composition of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the Cross River Estuary, Nigeria. (December, 2010)**

S/n	Total length(m)	Wet weight(g)	Food volume(mc)	Condition factor(k)
1	15.0	60	3.0	1.78
2	16.0	80	4.0	1.95
3	15.0	60	3.0	1.78
4	12.0	40	2.0	2.31
5	12.0	50	2.0	2.89
6	14.0	80	5.0	2.92
7	14.0	100	5.0	3.64
8	16.0	80	5.0	1.95
9	17.0	80	4.0	1.63
10	15.0	60	3.0	1.78
11	12.0	60	3.0	3.47
12	10.5	40	2.0	3.46
13	11.0	40	2.0	3.01
14	12.0	40	2.0	2.31
15	13.0	60	3.0	2.73
16	14.0	100	4.0	3.64
17	14.0	100	4.0	3.64
18	12.0	60	3.0	3.47
19	11.0	50	3.0	3.76
20	11.0	60	3.0	4.50
21	10.0	60	3.0	6.00
22	11.0	80	4.0	6.01
23	14.0	100	5.0	3.64
24	16.0	120	6.0	2.93
25	18.0	140	8.0	2.40
Total				77.6
Mean				3.10

Table 1c: Length (cm) Weight (g) Food Volume (ml) Condition Factors (k) and Diet Composition of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the Cross River Estuary, Nigeria. (January, 2011).

S/n	Total length(m)	Wet weight(g)	Food volume(mc)	Condition factor(k)
1	18.0	60	40	1.03
2	16.5	40	4.0	0.89
3	16.0	60	3.0	1.46
4	15.0	80	4.0	2.37
5	18.0	40	4.0	0.69
6	16.0	80	3.0	1.95
7	18.0	100	5.0	1.71
8	14.0	120	6.0	4.37
9	16.0	120	7.0	2.93
10	17.0	60	8.0	1.22
11	18.0	40	5.0	0.69
12	16.0	40	3.0	0.98
13	16.0	80	3.0	1.95
14	18.0	100	5.0	1.71
15	16.0	60	5.0	1.46
16	18.0	80	3.0	1.37
17	17.0	80	4.0	1.63
18	16.0	60	4.0	1.46
19	14.0	60	3.0	2.19
20	18.0	50	3.0	0.86
21	16.0	80	2.0	1.95
22	14.0	60	4.0	2.19
23	14.0	60	2.0	2.19
24	12.0	100	5.0	5.79
25	14.0	120	6.0	4.37
Total				49.41
Mean				1.98

Diet Components

The distribution of diet components during the study is shown in fig 2. In November, 2010, a total of 10 different diet components were recorded in the gut of *Ethmalosa fimbriata*, showing varying numerical abundance and relative percentage abundance. The diet was composed of diatoms 15 (12.0%), algae 14 (11.2%), aquatic insects parts 11 (8.8%), fish eggs 8 (6.4%), fish scales 3 (2.4%), unidentified food items 8 (6.8%), fish bones 6 (4.8%), plant materials 40 (32.0%), mud/sand particles 20 (16.0%) and detritus which could not be enumerated (Table 2a). The relative importance of the diet components in November followed the order: plant material > mud/sand particles > diatoms > algae > insects parts > fish eggs > unidentified food items > fish bones > fish scales > detritus.

In December, 2010, 10 diet components were also recorded in the gut of *E. fimbriata*. The diet components with their respective numerical and relative percentage abundance (fig 2) were plant materials 42 (33.33%), diatoms 15 (11.90%), algae 23 (18.25%), aquatic insects parts 11 (8.73%), fish eggs 6 (4.76%), fish scales 6 (4.76%), fish bones 7 (5.55%), unidentified food items 2 (1.58%), mud/sand particle 14 (11.11%) and detritus which could not be empirically determined (Table 2b). The relative importance of the diet components in December followed the order: plant materials > algae > diatoms > mud/sand particles > aquatic insects parts > fish bone > fish eggs > fish scales > unidentified food item > detritus.

Fig 2: Distribution of diets components in the gut of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* during the studied period (November – January, 2011).

In January, 2011, 10 different diet components were recorded in the gut of *E. fimbriata* (fig 2). Similar variations in numerical and relative percentage were also observed in the diet of the species during the months of study. These were plant material 38 (29.23%), diatoms 14 (10.76), algae 21 (16.15%), aquatic insects parts 18 (13.84%), fish eggs 8 (6.15), fish scales 5 (3.84), fish bones 4 (3.07), unidentified food items 6 (4.61), mud/sand particles 16 (12.30%) and detritus with no empirical value (Table 2c). The relative importance of the diet components in January followed the order: plant material > algae > aquatic insect part > mud/sand particles > diatoms > fish eggs > unidentified food items > fish scales > fish bones > detritus.

Table 2a: Diets composition, their numerical abundance and relative percentage abundance observed in the gut of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the cross river system, Nigeria. (November, 2010).

S/n	Diet Component	Numerical Abundance	% Relative Abundance
1	Plant material	40	32.0
2	Diatoms	15	12.0
3	Algae	14	11.2
4	Aquatic insects parts	11	8.8
5	Fish eggs	8	6.4
6	Fish scales	3	2.4
7	Fish bones	6	4.8
8	Unidentified food items	8	6.4
9	Mud/sand particle	20	16.0
10	Detritus	*	*
	Total	125	100.0

Table 2b: Diets composition, their numerical abundance and relative percentage abundance observed in the gut of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the cross river system, Nigeria. (December, 2010).

S/N	Diet component	Numerical Abundance	% Relative abundance
1	Plant material	42	33.33
2	Diatoms	15	11.90
3	Algae	23	18.25
4	Aquatic insect parts	11	8.73
5	Fish eggs	6	4.76
6	Fish scales	6	4.76
7	Fish bones	7	5.55
8	Unidentified food items	2	1.58
9	Mud/sand particle	14	11.11
10	Detritus	*	*
Total		126	99.97

Table 2c: Diets composition, their numerical abundance and relative percentage abundance observed in the gut of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* from the cross river system, Nigeria. (January, 2011).

S/N	Diet Component	Numerical Abundance	% Relative Abundance
1	Plant material	38	29.23
2	Diatoms	14	10.76
3	Algae	21	16.15
4	Aquatic insect parts	18	13.84
5	Fish eggs	8	6.15
6	Fish scales	5	3.84
7	Fish bones	4	3.07
8	Unidentified food items	6	4.61
9	Mud/sand particle	16	12.30
10	Detritus	*	*
Total		130	99.95

DISCUSSION

Examination of the gut contents of *Ethmalosa fimbriata* revealed that the species feed mostly on diets of plant origin. The diets components encounter in the gut of *E. fimbriata* during the study period include fish eggs, fish scales, unidentified food items, algae, diatoms, aquatic insect parts, fish bones, plant materials, mud/sand particles and detritus. Although 10 different diet components were encountered in the gut of the species during the investigation. However, diet components like fish eggs, fish scales, fish bone and unidentified food items had low percentage abundance during the study period.

The availability or otherwise of these diet component in the diet of the species in these months might have been due to the availability of a particular food item or due to size selection of diets by the species during the months of study.

Qin and Fost (1997) observed similar size selection in *Channa striatus* in South-east Asia as was similarly observed by Ng and Lim (1990) in the same area. In any aquatic ecosystem and main feeding habit of any fish indicates where such fish can be found (Moore and Moore, 1976). For example, the presence of mud/sand particles and detritus indicated bottom feeders, the assumption being that these items are abundant in the benthos and that the species may be a benthic feeder. This however, is merely a reasonable guess as these materials might have been incidental diet components which were obtained alongside the main diet components of the species in the habitat (Qin and Fost, 1997; Job and Nyong, 2005; Ajah et al., 2005).

The variations in numerical abundance of food items isolated in the gut of the species during the study period might be as a result of the availability or otherwise of a particular diet component in the gut of the species in the different month. This is a general event which coincides with either the period the diet components are available in the habitat or the phenomenon of ontogenicity in organisms (Haroon, 1998; Olojo et al., 2003; Wu and Culver, 1992; Ajah et al., 2005).

A total of 75 fishes were used for the study. 25 fishes were caught and studied in each sampling months. Variations in the numerical abundance of the diet components consumed by *Ethmalosa fimbriata* was also observed in each of the months. There were 125 in November, 126 in December and 130 in January. The variations might have been caused by an increase in the quantity of a particular food item in one month and a

reduction in one or another food item consumed by the species in the month during the study. This again agrees with the report of Onyia (1973) during his studies on a contribution to the food and feeding habits of the thread fin fish *Galeoides decadactylus* in Lagos Lagoon, Nigeria who attributed the variations in the food consumed by *G. decadactylus* to food preference and availability, Casta and Wanninayake (1986), when working on food, feeding and fecundity of the giant freshwater prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* from natural habitats in Srilanka, Okon (2002), when working on some aspects of the food and feeding habits of *Ilisha africana* from Qua Iboe River estuary, Nigeria, Ajah et al., (2005), when studying the food and feeding habits of five freshwater and brackish water fish species in Nigeria, Job and Udo (2002), when reporting on the food, feeding and the condition factor of the estuarine catfish *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus* of the Cross River, Nigeria.

The preference shown by a species to a diet component or group is a biological strategy which discouraged competition for available food resource within a species (Olojo et al., 2003; Job and Nyong, 2005).

The mean condition factor showed an interesting variation pattern. This ranged from 2.0 to 3.10. In November, condition factor was 2.0, in December the condition factor increased to 3.10 and a further reduction in January to a value of 1.98. These variations are indicative of the fact that in November and December, the species had good and varied diet components which might have been unconnected with favorable ecological conditions. These parameters might have continually undergone significant variations and changes resulting in the observed reduction in condition factor of the species in the habitat with time. In January, mean condition factor of the species reduced to 1.98 indicating either a period of unfavourable ecological conditions or a period which the species might have undergone stress from low food availability and/or reproductive processes. When an organism undergoes starvation or has become spent, its condition factor reduces even when every other ecological factor is optimum (Odum, 1971). This might have been the case during this study.

Similar observations were made by Job and Udo (2002) during their studies on the food, feeding and the condition factor of the estuarine catfish *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus* of the Cross River, Nigeria. Enin and Enidiok (2002) also reported monthly variations in the mean condition factor in *Cynoglossus senegalensis* in the Cross River Estuary, Nigeria which they attributed to environmental changes, state of growth and food availability which support the results of the present study.

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